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Senior High School Teacher Readiness in the Implementation of Learning From Home in Covid-19 Adaptation Period

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Abstract

This research is intended to determine senior high school teacher readiness in the implementation of Learning from Home in Covid-19 adaptation period. This was a policy evaluation research which used a mixed method approach in analyzing the data. Primary data was obtained from interviews via telephone and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) through Zoom. Sample's data were taken using purposive sampling technique in Banten and Gorontalo. The data analysis technique of this research was Miles and Huberman model. The results show that during the pandemic, all schools carried out learning from home. The average of lesson duration in a week is 1 to 3 hours. Learning carried out by some teachers is still pursuing the completeness of the curriculum for all subject matter. Assessment in learning used qualitative assessment. The conditions and facilities owned by the school are that most of the teachers face problems on the weak Internet connection disturbing the implementation of the teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Learning From Home, Covid-19 Adaptation Period

1. Introduction

Education is a process of transferring knowledge systematically from one person to another in accordance with the standards set by experts, so it can change attitudes, behavior, maturity to think and person's personality through formal, informal, or non-formal way (Moses, 2012: 18).

Education is a conscious and planned effort to create learning atmosphere and the learning process to make the students can actively develop their potential through religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character and skills needed by themselves, the community, the nation and the state. (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System Article 1 Paragraph 1). Therefore, it can be concluded that education is a conscious and planned effort in the form of knowledge transfer

from one person to another to realize active learning and ultimately be able to develop individual potential through formal, informal and non-formal ways.

The process of knowledge transfer in education involves teachers and students. Teachers are professional educators to educate, teach, guide, direct, train, assess and evaluate students in early childhood education through formal, basic and secondary education (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers Article 1 Paragraph 1).

Teacher has roles as demonstrator, mentor, class manager, mediator, facilitator and evaluator (Usman, 2011: 5). Besides, the teacher has important role in determining the students' success through effective learning, because basically, a teacher is someone who directly manages the Teaching and Learning Process (PBM). This is realized able to improve teacher performance. Teacher performance is a behavior or response giving a result and referring to what teachers do when facing certain tasks (Yamin & Maisah, 2010: 87).

In line with the development of teacher performance, this study was adjusted to the situation and conditions due to Covid-19 outbreak. This pandemic is a phenomenon spread of the Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19) caused by the coronavirus (Wikipedia, 2019). This virus quickly spreads almost all countries, including Indonesia. This serious problem makes the governments around the world have to implement policies to prevent the spread chain of the virus. Unlike other countries that have adopted lockdown policy, Indonesia adopts PSBB or Large-Scale Social Restriction policy.

Large-Scale Social Restriction or PSBB is a limitation on certain activities of residents in the suspected area infected by Covid-19 to prevent the spread of this virus (Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 9 of 2020 concerning Guidelines for Scaled Social Restrictions Large in the Context of Accelerated Handling of Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19) Article 1 Paragraph 1). The Large-Scale Social Restriction Policy (PSBB) was made by considering the impact and influence of Covid-19 so it would not be as big as lockdown. Other policies undertaken by the government are Social Distancing and Physical Distancing. This policy was created to limit social interactions with other people, reduce activities outside and stay at home. This has forced the majority of schools, madrasahs and higher institutions in Indonesia to close the PBM (Teaching and Learning Process) system, which is conducted through online learning system.

In online learning implementation is supported by the Minister of Education and Culture Circular Letter Number 4 of 2020 concerning Implementation of Education Policies in an Emergency for the Spread of Covid-19 in point 2, namely the learning from home process which is carried out with the following conditions (1) Learning from home or distance learning is implemented to provide meaningful learning experiences for students, without being burdened with demands to complete all curriculum achievements for grade promotion and graduation; (2) Learning from home can focus on life skills education, including the pandemic issues; (3) Learning from home activities and assignments may vary between students, according to the interests and conditions of each student, including considering gaps in access or learning facilities at home; and (4) evidence or products of Learning from home activities are given qualitative and useful feedback from the teacher, without being required to give score or quantitative value.

One of the education levels affected by the Learning from Home (BDR) policy is Senior High School level. Senior High School (SMA) is a formal education unit providing general education at the senior education level as the following education steps of SMP, MTs or other forms of equivalent or advanced learning outcomes that are recognized as equal or equivalent to SMP or MTs (Government Regulation Republic of Indonesia Number 66 of 2010 concerning Amendments to Government Regulation Number 17 of 2010 concerning Management and Implementation of Education Article 1 Paragraph 13).

Online learning in the context of Learning from Home (BDR) aims to increase awareness and as a process to stop the spread of the virus through direct interaction among people. The transition from offline to online forces various parties to be able to follow the process and flow to make the learning system runs well.

Therefore, a study is needed on the readiness of high school teachers in learning from home. This is very important to do to find out the performance of teachers during the Covid-19 period in implementing the free learning policy. This is due to the figure of a teacher is the main key in implementing independent learning. It is very important to conduct a study related to teacher performance in the implementation of independent learning during the pandemic.

The problem in this research is how is the readiness of high school (SMA) teachers in disadvantaged, frontier and outermost areas (3T) in implementing Learning from Home during the Covid-19 adaptation period? The purpose of this study focuses on five aspects, including during the Covid-19 transmission carrying out learning from home, the duration of learning (direct interaction with students) through communication media in a week, the learning carried out is still pursuing completion of the curriculum for all subject matter, assessment (feedback) during or after the learning process from home, as well as the conditions and facilities owned by the school (Internet connection).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Teacher Performance

Performance is something describing the big responsibility of a person's job to exceed the standards that have been set (Uno & Lamatenggo, 2014: 60). Teacher performance, namely the behavior and response of a teacher which refers to things that are done when facing a task and involves all activities or behavior experienced by the teacher to provide results and goals for students (Yamin & Maisah, 2010: 31).

Factors that influence teacher performance include environment, individual characteristics, organizational characteristics, job characteristics, management behavior, job design, teacher performance appraisal, feedback, and organizational financial administration (Supardi, 2014: 50). Teachers must have various professional abilities in the implementation of Teaching and Learning Activities (KBM), namely mastering learning materials and strategies, mastering the methods to be used, mastering guidance and counseling, and mastering learning evaluation (Ahmad, 2017: 137).

2.2. Learning From Home (BDR)

Learning from Home or BDR is a solution in implementing social distancing to prevent the spread of the Covid-19 outbreak, because this learning system is carried out online remotely, it is also called learning carried out by students wherever and whenever (Handarini & Wulandari, 2020: 502). Learning from Home (BDR) is a government step or policy to prevent students from gathering in the form of a crowd, so it can hinder the opportunities for the spread of Covid-19 (Rasyid & Aswadi, 2020: 2).

A teacher is required to be able to design Learning from Home (BDR) activities that are lighter and more effective, but still creative by using the right media according to the material to be delivered (Kurniasari, 2020: 7). The types of assignments given by the teacher must be designed so the students remain enthusiastic in learning even though they are online and do not become a psychological burden for students. Learning from Home (BDR) provides wider opportunities for teachers to explore the material to be taught, but teachers must also be able to choose and limit the extent to which the appropriate application material covers the materials and learning methods used.

The four objectives of implementing Learning from Home (BDR) during the Covid-19 emergency period include (1) ensuring the fulfillment of students' rights to receive educational services during the Covid-19 emergency; (2) protecting education unit residents from the adverse effects of Covid-19; (3) preventing the spread and transmission of Covid-19 in educational units; and (4) ensuring the fulfillment of psychosocial support for educators, students, and parents or guardians (Minister of Education and Culture Circular Letter

Number 15 of 2020 concerning Guidelines for Organizing Learning from Home in an Emergency for the Spread of Coronavirus disease (Covid-19)).

The principles of implementing Learning from Home (BDR) during the Covid-19 emergency, are (1) the safety and mental health of students, educators, heads of education units, and all members of the education unit are the main; (2) Learning from Home (BDR) activities are carried out to provide meaningful learning experiences for students, without being burdened with demands to complete all curriculum achievements; (3) Learning from Home (BDR) can focus on life skills education ; (4) learning materials are inclusive in accordance with the age and level of education, cultural context, character, and the type of specificity of students; (5) activities and assignments during Learning from Home (BDR) may vary between regions, educational units, and students according to their respective interests and conditions and taking into account gaps in access to Home Learning facilities (BDR); (6) the learning outcomes of students during Learning from Home (BDR) are given qualitative and useful feedback from the teacher without being required to give a score or quantitative value; and (7) prioritizing positive patterns of interaction and communication between teachers and parents or guardians (Minister of Education and Culture Circular Letter Number 15 of 2020 concerning Guidelines for Organizing Learning from Home in an Emergency for the Spread of Coronavirus disease).

2.3. The Covid-19 Outbreak

Covid-19 was declared by the World Health Organization or WHO as a pandemic on March 12, 2020 (Fitriani, 2020: 194). A pandemic is an epidemic that occurs simultaneously everywhere, covering a large geographical area or an epidemic spreading to almost all countries or continents and it affects many people (Resti, 2020: 1). The example of pandemic is Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19). This disease should be given more attention because it can be transmitted quickly having mortality rate that cannot be ignored and there is no definitive therapy (Susilo, 2020: 63).

3. Research Methods

This research is part of the continuation of the Puslitjak Rapid Survey in April 2020 and the study of Teacher Performance in the Implementation of Freedom of Learning during the Covid-19 Pandemic which was conducted in June 2020. The research method in this study uses a mixed method approach. Mixed method is a research method that combines two research methods at once, namely qualitative and quantitative methods, so that more comprehensive, reliable, valid, and objective data are obtained (Sugiyono, 2011: 18). The study was carried out.

Primary data on the implementation of Learning from Home (BDR) was obtained from interviews through telephone and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) conducted through Zoom during the pandemic. Then, the data was processed to obtain information about the readiness of senior high school teachers in implementing Learning from Home during the Covid-19 adaptation period. Sampling in this study was purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling technique is a technique in determining the sample in an area with certain category in accordance with the objectives to be achieved. Purposive sampling technique is also defined as a sampling technique using certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2018: 300).

The sample used in this research was high school teachers in Banten and Gorontalo. The sample of senior high school teachers selected for Banten was Lebak Regency, while Gorontalo was North Gorontalo District. These two districts were chosen because they were included in the category of disadvantaged, frontier and outermost (3T) areas in Indonesia.

The data analysis technique used in this research was Miles and Huberman model and is carried out interactively and continuously, so the data obtained is valid. Activities in the data analysis of Miles and Huberman model include data collection, data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusion and verification (Miles & Huberman, 2014: 16).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Result

During the Covid-19 Pandemic Schools Carrying Out Learning from Home, based on a rapid analysis survey from Puslitjak which was carried out in April 2020 nationally, it was found that the reasons for schools that had not carried out learning from home were as follows.

Table 1: Reasons for Schools Not Conducting (BDR)

No.	Reason	Percentage
1.	There is no internet / supporting equipment	30,8%
2.	Located in a special area / hinterland	23,1%
3.	areas not affected by Covid-19	11,5%
4.	No local government policy	11,5%
5.	School closed	7,7%
6.	Others	3,8%

Source: Puslitjak Survey, 2020

The reason why most schools in 3T areas do not learn from home is because they do not have Internet or supporting devices. In the other hand, in the study locus of teachers' readiness in learning from home in Lebak Regency, Banten and North Gorontalo District, Gorontalo as a school has carried out learning from home, despite having lack of internet support.

4.1.1. The Learning Duration through Communication Media in a Week

Based on the readiness of senior high school teachers in implementing Learning from Home during the Covid-19 adaptation period, the duration of learning (direct interaction with students) through communication media in a week is grouped into four, including 1-3 hours, 4-6 hours, 7 -9 hours and 10 hours or more.

Based on a quick analysis survey from Puslitjak which was conducted nationally in April 2020 found that the average learning duration hours per week is 9.1 hours. When deepening is carried out to teachers in the implementation of Learning from Home (BDR) during the adaptation period Covid-19, then the length of time for implementing learning or direct interaction with students through communication media according to interviews in the respondent's area at one of the SMA Negeri Lebak Regency is recorded in the following note.

"The learning time is adjusted to the learning schedule in the subject matter, but the teacher's interaction with students through screen-to-screen varies. There are 30 minutes until one hour to explain through a power point presentation. Then continued with assignment, but most of the teachers give 24 hours free to contact the teacher if they have difficulties. "

This is the case when conducting an interview in one senior high school in North Gorontalo District that the learning duration was carried out as usual, but the teacher provided the opportunity to ask questions whenever the students want. This is due to the limited availability of Internet package for students and teachers, so screen time is limited. In addition, according to information from the teacher, if it takes too long to stare at the screen, it will make the students boring. This results in not being able to achieve mastery in learning.

4.1.2. Conducted Learning is still Pursuing Completeness of Curriculum

Based on the readiness of senior high school teachers in implementing Learning from Home during the Covid-19 adaptation period, the learning is still pursuing the completeness of the curriculum for all subject matter which is grouped into yes and no.

Questions from the 2020 Puslitjak Survey, whether teachers are still pursuing completeness of the curriculum from 1,041 respondents, 51.6% (537 respondents) yes and 48.4% (504 respondents) no. Based on in-depth interviews in senior high school of Lebak Regency, the curriculum used was K-13 which was adapted to the conditions of distance learning. The teacher was more conveying the main material (KI or KD). This was because of the situations and conditions of learning carried out online.

The teachers hope that the adapted curriculum to online learning can be easily implemented. The obstacle faced in preparation for learning is unstable Internet connection. Some teachers do not pursue completeness of the curriculum, because the learning conditions experience difficulty communicating through weak Internet connection. Some teachers are pursuing completeness of the curriculum, but teachers still face the limited learning duration and conditions for supporting facilities in learning, such as the availability of Internet networks.

4.1.3. Assessment at or After the Home Learning Process

Based on the readiness of high school teachers in implementing Learning from Home during the Covid-19 adaptation period, the assessment (feedback) during or after the learning process from home is grouped into four, including quantitative, qualitative, quantitative and qualitative assessments and did not give an assessment.

Based on the Puslitjak Survey, most teachers in providing assessment used qualitative and quantitative assessment amounted 46.1%. This can be seen from interview result with a teacher at Senior High School in Lebak Regency that the feedback in the online learning process is well packaged and attractive gives positive response to students. Students are interested in learning given through simple media. The teacher always appreciates the work or assignments given by students as positive feedback, for example in the form of positive praise or giving good grades. Another example is the task of making videos related to Covid-19 uploaded on social media that gets the most likes will get prizes and get the best comments directly from the teacher. This feedback is very important as motivation and also as student work reflection.

The teacher employed qualitative and score. The teacher did not force the target achieved; the important thing was the learning process was running well. If there was a missing assignment, the teacher helped in explaining the problems faced by students. The teacher reviewed the assignment submitted by students. In teacher's perspective, the teacher is not satisfied with the results of the assessment or feedback from students, because the assessment target is not achieved. This means that during the academic period, the teacher was unable to provide maximum teaching material compared to the face-to-face learning. The form of teacher feedback assessment is detailly described as follows.

Table 2: Forms of Teacher Feedback Assessment

No.	Assesment	Percentage
1.	Provide a qualitative & quantitative assessment	46,1%
2.	Provide quantitative assessment (score, numbers, points, & alphabet)	28,1%
3.	Provide a qualitative assessment (comments, notes, & appreciation)	21,3%
4.	Did not give assessment	4,5%

Source: Puslitjak Survey, 2020

4.1.4. Conditions and Facilities Owned by the School

Based on the readiness of high school teachers in implementing Learning from Home during the Covid-19 adaptation period, it was found that the conditions and facilities owned by schools (internet) were still experiencing problems.

Lack of teacher facilities in carrying out interactions with students is an obstacle in the learning process use this learning system. Most teachers face obstacles in Internet acces. Based on the Puslitjak Survey data, teachers face network constraints reaches 68.6%. In detail, the data can be seen in the following table.

Table 3: Teacher Obstacles in BDR

No.	Obstacle	Percentage
1.	Inadequate network / Internet package	68,6%
2.	Difficult to observe student development	68,2%
3.	Many students have difficulty learning from home	58,2%
4.	Difficult to coordinate with parents of students	31,3%
5.	Not yet able to optimize digital media	28,2%

Source: Puslitjak Survey, 2020

Based on the readiness of teachers in the implementation of Learning from Home (BDR) during the Covid-19 adaptation period through interviews at one of the Lebak Regency High Schools, learning from home in various forms, both online or online that utilizes information and communication technology as well as offline or offline has been running six months since the Covid-19 pandemic.

In its implementation, Learning from Home (BDR) has also encountered many obstacles, for example from a geographical aspect it has created a bias between cities and 3T areas. The availability of electricity and Internet connection are the most crucial problems that usually occur in 3T areas. Internet connection availability and frequent blackouts often hinder the learning process from home and not all student homes have internet access. The children's struggle to obtain Internet connection is pursued in various ways, starting from riding in neighboring villages with strong signals, climbing into trees, studying in the hills and not infrequently students looking for signals at night to get smoother Internet connection.

Figure 1: Students Searching for Internet Connection by Climbing to Trees in Mumunggang Cigemblong Village, Lebak Regency

Other obstacle faced is students who do not have mobile phone as a means of supporting learning activities from home. This is because most of the residents are in the middle to lower category economic. Another case, students who have cellphones, but they cannot buy Internet package. The solidarity and mutual here is still evident.

Students who have cellphones do not hesitate to share with others, for example, sometimes students have to join forces to buy Internet package. The role of Facebook is also quite helpful with its free mode, but this of course has drawbacks, because it cannot open images or videos.

5. Discussion

Based on the results of the data analysis above, it can be argued that the reason most schools in 3T areas cannot carry out Learning from Home (BDR) activities is due to the lack of support for adequate Internet network facilities. This case causes teachers face the limitations in providing adequate learning or study duration for students.

Teachers in the 3T area do not impose the achievement of learning targets on students. For teachers, the most important thing is that the learning activity process can run well, that is, the teacher is able to provide feedback or help to explain the problems faced by students. The obstacles experienced by students during the Learning from Home (BDR) process are inadequate internet and electricity networks and students who did not have mobile phone and could not even buy Internet package.

Based on this discussion, the teacher as a teaching staff must be able to prepare solutions occurring in the process of Learning from Home (BDR) activities. The readiness of the teacher in preparing the learning process is the key in the successful learning. Therefore, in the conditions of the Covid-19 adaptation period, it requires teachers to innovate and be creative in learning adapted to existing conditions. This is in accordance with the opinion of Untari (2020: 53) which states that "teacher creativity in facing learning during the Pandemic is very much needed, so there is a need for more intense coaching as an effort to improve the abilities of each teacher." What is important for teachers is also the support from management, in this case the principal, to provide motivation and facilities in the implementation of learning from home.

6. Conclusion And Suggestion

6.1. Conclusion

The results show that during the Covid-19 outbreak, all schools carried out learning from home. The duration of learning (direct interaction with students) through communication media in a week on average is 1 to 3 hours. The learning that is being carried out is still pursuing the completeness of the curriculum for all subject matter. Assessment (feedback) during or after the home learning process uses a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessments. The condition and facilities owned by the school (Internet) is the limited Internet connection in the 3T area.

6.2. Suggestion

Therefore, several suggestions can be formulated, including the need for training for teachers who are less skilled in using social media. For example, increasing the teachers' ability to prepare teaching materials through interactive power point. Besides, it is necessary to arrange modules or a summary of the main subjects to be conveyed in learning from home. Subject-related learning taught by the teacher must be encouraged to connect with potential to environment. The government needs to measure or assess basic competencies that cannot be achieved in learning due to the limited interaction between teachers and students. Therefore, it needs to be an emphasis on the main basic competencies that students have to master. Besides, the government needs to provide adequate facilities to support the implementation of the Learning from Home (BDR) policy during the Covid-19 adaptation period.

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